

HOW QUALITY OF WORK LIFE, SELF-EFFICACY, AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT BOOSTING EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION: A CASE STUDY AT MOTHER AND CHILD HOSPITAL

Fakhrana Nasaruddin ^{1*}, Fridawaty Rivai ², M. Alimin Maidin ³,
Syahrir A. Pasinringi ⁴, Noer Bahry Noer ⁵ and Nurmala Sari ⁶

¹ Master's Student of Hospital Administration Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia. *Corresponding Author Email: fakhranan21@gmail.com
^{2,3,4,5,6} Hospital Administration Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia.

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Abstract

Background. Job satisfaction is one of the important things in work psychologists and is used to determine the quality of the health care system. If people with high job satisfaction have positive feelings about their work while people with low job satisfaction have negative emotions. The low percentage of job satisfaction in RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah is 70.3 % (Standard 76.61-88,30% According to Permanpan-RB No. 14 of 2021). There are several factors that affect job satisfaction, one of which is QWL, Self-Efficacy and organizational commitment where the three variables have an impact on job satisfaction. Purpose. This research aims to analyse the influence of QWL, Self-efficacy, and organizational commitment to job satisfaction at RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah. **Method.** This research is a quantitative research with a cross-sectional design, which was conducted at RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah, from February 2024 to March 2024. The population in this study consisted of 259 at RSKD Pertiwi and 209 at RSKDIA St. Fatimah with a sample of 300 samples selected using the accidental sampling method. Data is collected using questionnaires. **Results.** The results of statistical data research show that QWL is known that it has no significant effect on employee job satisfaction ($p = 0.997$) and organizational commitment also has no significant effect on job satisfaction ($p = 0.600$), while Self Efficacy ($p=0.002$) shows a significant influence on job satisfaction on employees. In addition, the results of the comparison of QWL, Self-efficacy, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction show that there is no significant difference in RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah ($p=0.126$, $p=0.088$, $p=0.976$ and $p=0.144$). **Conclusion.** Based on the results of the research, it can be known that the QWL variable and organizational commitment do not have an influence on job satisfaction, while for self-efficacy, there is an influence on job satisfaction. After being analysed, it is known that to improve QWL and commitment, the organization must have a high commitment to the organization. If employees choose a high organizational commitment, employees will remain in the organization and will continue to improve their performance, the organization does not need to carry out strict supervision if the organization's commitment in high employees and hospitals and improves the welfare of employees in hospitals, where employees can be appreciated and supported.

Keywords: Quality of Work Life; Self Efficacy; Organizational Commitment; Job Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Attention to human resources is very important to obtain employee performance as expected in order to achieve the vision, mission and goals of the organization. Employee performance is a phenomenon related to aspects of effectiveness, knowledge management, quality, management, financing, organizational development. Especially for the performance problems of doctors and nurses closely related to patient safety (Platis, Rekitis, & Zimeras, 2015). The cooperation of various personnel such as nurses with doctors and hospital management is needed because it greatly affects performance (van Bogaer et al, 2013).

The quality of performance in the health sector such as Hospitals largely depends on the health care provider. This is because the high demands of the public to get quality health services require satisfied staff (Martins., et al, 2016). Therefore, job satisfaction is an important thing to study.

According to research that has been done that managers who have successfully managed their work show that the implications of employee job satisfaction are directly related to employee productivity, workplace attendance level, and employee entry and exit rate. (Tampubolon, 2008). Job satisfaction is one of the important variables in occupational and organizational psychology that is considered as an indicator of the quality of work life and is an important variable used to determine the quality of the health care system (Khamlub et al., 2013) People with high job satisfaction have positive feelings about their work while people with low job satisfaction have negative emotions. (Liu., et al, 2016).

In QWL, the research in line conducted by Rinanti (2018) at RSIA X Surabaya shows that there is a positive influence of QWL on satisfaction with a significance value of 0.024 or $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that the increase in quality of work life is in line with employee job satisfaction. While self-efficacy based on the results of research and data processing shows that self-esteem and self-efficacy have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at Ciamis Hospital with a 44.5% effect.

While the remaining 55.5% is influenced by other factors which means that the influence caused is a positive influence. This shows that self-efficacy has a positive effect on job satisfaction. And finally on the organizational commitment of the research results at the Sidoarjo Regency Hospital, it was found that there was a positive influence on the organization's commitment to the job.

In the initial data collection during the internship at RSKD Pertiwi South Sulawesi Province in September 2022 which was carried out by measuring the job satisfaction of employees at RSKD Pertiwi South Sulawesi Province who were known to have not reached the standard of only 70.3%. While RSKDIA Siti Fatimah South Sulawesi Province is 70.3 % (Standard: 76.61% -88.30 % According to Permenpan-RB No. 14 Year 2017). Job satisfaction is a person's general attitude in dealing with his work, someone who is high job satisfaction has a positive attitude towards his work, while someone who does not get satisfaction in his work has a negative attitude towards his work (Sofyandi and Garniwa, 2007).

The comparison of Fatimah Hospital and Pertiwi Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR) at Pertiwi Hospital in South Sulawesi Province is still very far below the standard which is only 43.83% by 2023. In addition, the BOR at RSKDIA Siti Fatimah South Sulawesi Province is 35.43 in 2023 (60-85% Standard According to the Ministry of Health, 2006).

On the organizational culture in RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah focuses on providing high quality services to mothers and children, collaborating between various departments and staff, and reflecting concern for the physical and social environment. Therefore, researchers are interested to see the influence of RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA Siti Fatimah, South Sulawesi Province.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Data Collection, samples and measurements

This research is to analyse the influence of quality of work life, self-efficacy of the organization's commitment to job satisfaction on employees of RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah Province of South Sulawesi by using quantitative research with a cross sectional approach. The population of this research is RSKDIA Pertiwi employees which numbered 259 people and RSKDIA St. Fatimah in South Sulawesi Province with a total of 209 people including doctors, dentists, nurses, midwives, pharmacists and pharmacist assistants, laborers, radiographers, dietician, physiotherapy, and other personnel. Sampling using the slovin formula with an error margin of 5% so that the number of samples obtained at RSKDIA Pertiwi is 160 people and RSKDIA St. Fatimah 140 people to employees at RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah, South Sulawesi Province. Sampling technique using accidental sampling with inclusion and exclusion criteria.

2.2 Data Analysis

Data processing and analysis techniques used in this study use a nominal scale. Data analysis using Man Whitney test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

Table 1: Distribution of employee characteristics at RSKD Pertiwi and RSKDIA Siti Fatimah South Sulawesi Province

Characteristic	Workplace; f (%)		Total (n=300)
	RSKD Pertiwi (n=155)	RSKDIA Siti Fatimah (n=145)	
Age			
20-30 years old	33 (21.3%)	25 (17.2%)	58 (19.3%)
31-40 years old	74 (47.7%)	53 (36.6%)	127 (42.3%)
41-50 years old	39 (25.2%)	52 (35.9%)	91 (30.3%)
>50 years old	9 (5.8%)	15 (10.3%)	24 (8%)
Working period			
1-5 years	54 (34.8%)	39 (26.9%)	93 (31%)
6-10 years	26 (16.8%)	23 (15.9%)	49 (16.3%)
>10 years	75 (48.4%)	83 (57.2%)	158 (52.7%)
Profession			
Doctors	3 (1.9%)	6 (4.1%)	9 (3%)
Dentists	1 (0.6%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.3%)
Nurse	44 (28.4%)	30 (20.7%)	74 (24.7%)
Midwife	38 (24.5%)	38 (26.2%)	76 (25.3%)
Pharmacist	12 (7.7%)	3 (2.1%)	15 (5%)
Laboratory	1 (0.6%)	5 (3.4%)	6 (2%)
Radiographer	0 (0%)	5 (3.4%)	5 (1.7%)
Dietician	1 (0.6%)	3 (2.1%)	4 (1.3%)
Physiotherapy	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.7%)	2 (0.7%)
Other Personnel	54 (34.8%)	54 (37.2%)	108 (36%)
Gender			
Man	20 (12.9%)	12 (8.3%)	32 (10.7%)
Woman	135 (87.1%)	133 (91.7%)	268 (89.3%)

Characteristic	Workplace; f (%)		Total (n=300)
	RSKD Pertiwi (n=155)	RSKDIA Siti Fatimah (n=145)	
Last education			
SMA	6 (3.9%)	7 (4.8%)	13 (4.3%)
Diploma	49 (31.6%)	58 (40%)	107 (35.7)
S1	66 (42.6%)	52 (35.9%)	118 (39.3%)
Profession/specialist	22 (14.2%)	20 (13.8%)	42 (14%)
S2	12 (7.7%)	8 (5.5%)	20 (6.7%)
Employment status			
Contract employees	21 (13.5%)	29 (20%)	50 (16.7%)
Permanent employees	3 (1.9%)	5 (3.4%)	8 (2.7%)
Civil servants	131 (84.5%)	111 (76.6%)	242 (80.7%)

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents' characteristics in both hospitals including age, period of employment, profession, gender, last education and employment status. When viewed from the age of the majority of respondents, they are in the age group of 31-40 years with a dominant working period of >10 years. When viewed from the profession, the two hospitals that are the most research respondents are other personnel followed by midwives and nurses. Based on gender, most employees are women with a ratio of 8:1 in the sense that of the 8 female employees there is 1 male employee. When viewed from the last education, in RSKDIA Pertiwi the majority of scholars (42.6%) while in RSKDIA Siti Fatimah the majority of diplomas (40%) and most of the employees have the status of civil servants. Based on age, in RSKDIA Pertiwi the average employee is 37 years old with the youngest age of 23 years and the oldest is 59 years while in RSKDIA Siti Fatimah the average is 39 years old (minimum 23 years old and maximum 28 years). For the working period, employees at RSKD Pertiwi have an average working period of 11 years and at RSKDIA Siti Fatimah have an average of 13 years with the fastest working period of 1 year and the longest 35 years.

Table 2: The simultaneous influence of quality of work life, self-efficacy and organizational commitment to job satisfaction to employees at RSKD Pertiwi and RSKDIA Siti Fatimah South Sulawesi Province.

Step	Variable	p-value*	OR	CI95%	R ²
Model 1	Quality of work life	0.997	775.9	0.0 – 0.0	0.933
	Self-efficacy	0.002	228.1	7.09 – 7339.4	
	Organizational commitment	0.600	2.40	0.090 – 64.2	
Model 2	Self-efficacy	<0.001	1223.7	96.2 – 15563.1	0.880
	Organizational commitment	0.052	18.3	0.9 – 343.0	

*Backward-Wald method multiple logistic regression test; dependent variable = job satisfaction

Table 2 shows variables that simultaneously affect job satisfaction and appear to produce 2 models and only the qualified 2nd model is included in the final equation. The determination coefficient (R²) shows a substantial correlation between self-efficacy and the organization's commitment to job satisfaction (0.880) which means that 88% of job satisfaction variance can be explained by variable self-efficacy and organizational commitment while 12% is influenced by other variables. Of all the independent variables, the most influential on job satisfaction is the self-efficacy variable with p value <0.001. The largest OR value obtained is 1223.7, meaning that high self-efficacy has a chance of 1223.7 times increasing job satisfaction for employees at RSKD Pertiwi and RSKDIA Siti Fatimah, South Sulawesi Province.

3.2 Discussion

From the results of the research it is known that commitment and self-efficacy affect job satisfaction, but after further analysis that self-efficacy was found to be very influential between the three variables. Self-efficacy is one of the most influential aspects of self-knowledge in daily life. 'Self-efficacy is a person's belief about his chances of successfully achieving a certain task' Keitner and Kinicki (2014). From the results of other research shows that self-efficacy can increase employee job satisfaction. This is proven in the results of Purnama & Manuatu (2014) research which states that high self-efficacy will cause high job satisfaction and is supported by the results of Lai (2012) research, which states that employees with high self-efficacy have superior job abilities and can improve job satisfaction obtained from their work. How to increase a person's self-efficacy so that it has an impact on employee satisfaction by providing support to employees in facing challenges, namely giving responsibility gradually to employees to expand experience and increase confidence in dealing with tasks, giving appreciation for employee achievements that can increase self-confidence in them. and lastly providing a positive, inclusive, and motivating work environment so that a positive work Susana can help build employee self-confidence.

Self-efficacy is divided into several dimensions, namely problem solving, perseverance, and common sense.. The results of the per dimensional univariate distribution research found that the problem solving dimension in RSKDIA Pertiwi is 91% higher than other dimensions. While RSKDIA St. Fatimah the dimension of perseverance and common sense is 94.5 %. Overall, RSKDIA employees have a high majority self-efficacy in the problem solving dimension and the common sense dimension of 92.3 each. This shows that these two dimensions are all employees of RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St., Fatimah has a high majority in both dimensions. The research conducted on (Rachel, 2022) found a positive influence on the problem solving dimension and the common sense dimension on satisfaction.

In addition to self-efficacy, organizational commitment also affects job satisfaction in this research even though the organization's committee is not the most variable has a big influence on the employee's job satisfaction in this research. Organizational commitment is very influential on employee job satisfaction because of the attachment that has a high level of organization to the organization and feels satisfied with work. To increase the organization's commitment to employees by increasing open communication so that employees feel that information about development and change strategies is conveyed clearly and transparently, creating a comfortable supportive work environment and lastly rewarding employee achievement.

Organizational Commitment is divided into several dimensions, namely Continuance commitment, normative commitment, and affective commitment. In the distribution of univariate organization commitments, the results were obtained that showed RSKDIA Pertiwi employees the highest dimension of the affective dimension was 87.1 % and for the low category dimension was the normative commitment dimension (29.7%). While RSKDIA St. Fatimah has a high dimension of affective commitment which is 91.7% and the low category is the normative dimension. Therefore, as a whole, employees at RSKDIA have a high majority organizational commitment in the affective commitment dimension (89.3%). This study is in line with the results of the hypothesis test, it can be concluded that Affective Commitment (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance seen from the original estimate sample has a positive

value of 0.447 which shows the direction of a positive relationship, and seen from the t-statistical value is smaller than t-table $3,374 > 1,662$ and the significance level has a value of 0.001 ($P < 0.05$). So it can be concluded that affective commitment has a positive and significant effect on the proactive work behaviour of employees (Nanda, 2022).

The result of self-efficacy and influential commitment, QWL is also very influential on job satisfaction. QWL is a concept that describes the perception of employees towards meeting needs through work experience in the organization, so that the goal of the quality of work life can be aligned with the management function to manage superior human resources and have maximum work productivity and the employee gets personal satisfaction for meeting their needs (Brooks & Anderson, 2005). The existence of a positive influence of QWL on Job Satisfaction is supported by research conducted by (Setiyadi and Wartini, 2016) which shows that QWL has a positive influence on job satisfaction. Research conducted by (Winasih, Nursalam and K, 2015) found that QWL has a significant influence on Nurse Job Satisfaction at RSUD Dr. Soetomo Surabaya. And to increase QWL towards job satisfaction, namely contributing by giving awards, providing opportunities to develop abilities through training or further education, and balanced employee workload so that employees do not feel depressed or stressed.

In the per dimensional univariate distribution research, the dimensions of physical & social security and the dimensions of collaboration & identity were obtained, namely 92.3%. This shows that these two dimensions are all employees of RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah has a high majority in both dimensions.. This research is in line with Lau et al, (2001) describing QWL as a work environment that supports and increases satisfaction by providing rewards, job safety, and opportunities to develop careers to employees. QWL in this research is interpreted as a process carried out by an organization in ensuring employee welfare, work safety, job satisfaction, good reward system, employee benefits, employee involvement in achieving the goals set by an organization. Human competence represents the knowledge-based success factor of an organization and is included in the measurement of self-esteem factors. Physical and emotional security is the foundation of a good QWL, while excessive stress and fear negatively impact employee well-being and productivity. The collaboration and identity factors are mostly associated with group motivation, while the goal and creativity factors refer to the positive attitude and enthusiasm of employees (Kesti et al., 2016).

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be seen that the QWL variable, self-efficacy and organizational commitment have a large comparison of job satisfaction between RSKDIA Pertiwi and RSKDIA St. Fatimah although $p > 0.05$ is not significant. Therefore, to improve QWL, self-efficacy and commitment, the hospital is able to improve the welfare of the people, see the abilities of employees, and create a positive work culture where all employees feel appreciated and lack of discrimination. This research can be done again if this research explores more insight into QWL-related phenomena, self-efficacy and organizational commitment to employee performance owned by respondents.

Limitations of the Study

1. At the time of the research, the data collection process partly used google forms, which increased the risk or potential for bias because respondents could fill in without transparency and it was difficult to avoid manipulation of google forms.
2. Sample determination needs to consider a homogeneous proportion based on the profession of hospital employees. In the future in this study it is better to add a heterogeneous population of professions from other government-owned hospitals and private hospitals.

Conflict of Interest

There are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication

Authorship Contributions

The authors contributed to the conception, design, data collection, interpretation, analysis, and drafting of this research paper

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